

Neutron Activation of Sodium-Filled Heat Pipes for Space Reactors and Dose Estimations in Electronics

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ABSTRACT

Radiation shielding represents a critical challenge for space reactors, that must be compact, lightweight, and capable of reliable long-term operation. The electronic systems of such reactors are exposed to several radiation sources that must be properly attenuated to ensure sustained performance. In addition to cosmic rays and the primary neutron and photon flux emitted by the core, heat pipe-cooled reactor designs raise further concerns related to the activation of the working fluid. When the heat pipe fluid get activated within the reactor core, it can carry radioactive isotopes beyond the primary shielding. This process creates an additional radiation source that may significantly increase the dose absorbed by nearby electronics. The objective of this work is to estimate the impact of heat pipe fluid activation on the dose absorbed by electronic components and to evaluate its implications for the design and reliability of future space reactor systems. The present work investigates this phenomenon through a case study of a 200 kWt reactor using sodium heat pipes. The estimated activity for 10 years of operation is 2.66 GBq/g, with the dominant contribution arising from the decay of Na-24, while the effect of sodium impurities is found to be negligible. The resulting dose levels raise concerns about the ability of the electronics to withstand long-term operation, as they are comparable with conventional radiation tolerance limits (0.1–10 Mrad). Additional localized shielding or the implementation of an intermediate heat pipe loop may therefore be required to ensure the reliability of the system over its intended lifetime.

Keywords: Heat Pipe, Space Reactors, Sodium, Activation, Dose

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear reactors find potential use in space applications, where high power density, reliability, continuous and long-term operation are required. In particular, Heat Pipe Reactors (HPR) are particularly appealing for low to medium power levels applications such as spacecraft electric propulsion and as power supply for lunar habitats. Their passive cooling system allows for simple, compact, reliable and lightweight design, because of the reduced amount of components (e.g. pumps and valves). In fact, mass minimisation is one of the main design drivers for space reactors, since it directly affects launch costs and mission feasibility. However, mass minimisation is in contrast with the requirement to provide adequate radiation shielding for electronic components. Effective protection generally requires the use of thick radiation shields, which add significant mass to the system [1, 2]. The issue is particularly relevant in HPR that are directly connected (without an intermediate loop) to compact energy conversion systems that exploit nearby electronics, such as thermoelectric converters or Stirling engines. In these configurations (see Figure 1), the working fluid get activated as it passes through the reactor core and then circulates beyond the shield. This flow of radioactive material outside the core region introduces an additional radiation source that adds to the primary radiation emitted by the core (photons and neutrons) and to the cosmic rays (mainly protons and atomic nuclei). This work aims to quantify

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the radiation generated by neutron activation in heat pipes (HPs) and to assess its impact on electronic components, a contribution that, to our knowledge, has received little attention in the open literature. The neutron activation analysis is conducted on a representative space reactor configuration, which has been selected as a case study. This reactor features an epithermal spectrum and sodium-filled HPs [3].

Figure 1. Typical layout for a Heat Pipe Space Reactor.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study is divided into two analyses. The first aims to model the activation process and to compute the amount of radiation emitted by the HPs. The second analysis takes as input the previously computed activity, models the particle transport and the energy deposition in nearby electronics, and thus assesses the resulting dose.

2.1. The case study: a unmoderated 200 kWt heat pipe reactor

The neutron activation analysis is based on a reference 200 kWt HPR designed by Politecnico di Milano and Thales Alenia Space Italia (PoliMi-TASI) [3]. The reactor is conceived for space applications, especially as power supply for lunar habitat and low power nuclear electric propulsion. It features a monolithic uranium molybdenum fuel (19.75% enriched) surrounded by beryllium oxide reflector. It is cooled by sixty HPs, each filled with 89 g of sodium. HPs are arranged in three concentric circular rings (see Figure 2) and operate at approximately 1000 K. Geometrical details and the neutronic characterisation are made available in Boccelli et al. [3]. Since the coolant flows through both the fuel and reflector regions, its volume-averaged neutron spectrum includes contributions from the fast neutrons generated in the fuel and from thermalised ones, moderated in BeO reflector. Figure 2 shows the neutron spectra in the main reactor components (i.e. fuel, reflector and heat pipe's wick).

2.2. Sodium impurities and their decay chains

Since the effect of the impurities was not known *a priori*, it has been decided to include them in the assessment of the source activity. In Table I, the amount of sodium impurities is reported accordingly to two different sources [4, 5]. Among these, calcium, chlorine, iron and potassium are commonly mentioned and, because of that, have been considered in the activation study. The concentrations have been set to 250 ppm, 10 ppm, 20 ppm and 200 ppm respectively, as indicated by IAEA report [4]. As it is shown in Figure 3, most of the isotopes undergo β^- decay, and hence a mixed source of electrons and γ rays is expected from the activation of the coolant.

Among the neutron induced reactions only neutron capture has been considered due to its predominant cross section with respect the other means of interaction for most of the aforementioned nuclides [6].

Figure 2. (a) Schematic representation of the PoliMi-TASI reactor [3]. (b) Neutron spectrum in principal reactor's components. Adapted from Boccelli et al. [3].

	Concentration (ppm)		
	ref. A [4]	ref. B1 [5]	ref. B2 [5]
Barium	< 5	-	-
Carbon	-	-	7
Calcium	250	500	250
Cobalt	-	-	<1
Chlorine	<10	14	0.2
Chromium	-	-	1
Copper	-	1.2	-
Iron	20	3	5
Magnesium	-	8	2
Nickel	-	0.1	-
Oxygen	-	60	-
Potassium	200	200	5
Sulphur	-	10	0.8
Silicon	-	16	6

Table I. Impurities in Sodium from different references.

2.3. Mathematical modelling and assumptions

Coolant activation is computed using a lumped approach: neutron flux spectrum is averaged considering the volume occupied by liquid sodium (wick regions) and spectrum-averaged neutron capture cross sections are computed for each isotope, as reported in Figure 3. The governing model is based on the Bateman equation [7]. For each isotope of concentration C_i it is included a sink terms due to neutron activation $-\Phi\sigma_i C_i$ and radioactive decay $-\lambda_i C_i$, as well as the source terms $\sum_j \Phi\sigma_{j\rightarrow i} C_j$ and $\sum_j \lambda_{j\rightarrow i} C_j$, where $\sigma_{j\rightarrow i}$ and $\lambda_{j\rightarrow i}$ are the capture cross section and decay constant of nuclide j when the outcome of the reaction is the nuclide i and zero otherwise.

Radioisotopes exit the activation region and circulates in the HP following the vapour and liquid path eventually re-enter the activation zone after a circulation time Δt_c and undergo radioactive decay with a decay constant $\lambda_i = \ln(2)/T_{1/2}$ (see Figure 4). However, this decay can be neglected if $\Delta t_c \ll T_{1/2}/\ln(2)$. Through the calculation of the mean liquid and vapour velocities one can estimate the residence time outside the active region. Considering that the fluid operates at a temperature of ≈ 1000 K and at saturation conditions (thermophysical data from Heat Pipe Science and Technology, A. Faghri, [8]) and assuming that the mass flow rate is mainly dictated by the evaporation/condensation

Figure 3. Decay chains, isotopic abundance and neutron capture cross section of Sodium and its impurities.

process, $\dot{m} = \dot{Q}/h_{lv}$ (with \dot{Q} the power input and h_{lv} the heat of vaporisation), it follows a mean liquid velocity $v_l \approx 0.013$ m/s and a vapour velocity $v_{vapour} \approx 54$ m/s. Because of the huge difference between the two speeds, vapour transit time can be neglected, resulting in $\Delta t_c \approx L_{inactive}/v_{liquid} = 38$ s. Considering the shortest-lived radionuclide impurity (Cl-38) the condition required to neglect the fluid circulation becomes $\Delta t_c \ll 3.2 \times 10^3$ s, which is satisfied. The mathematical model (Equation 1) is

Figure 4. Heat pipe schematics, working principle and isotope circulation. Grey region corresponds to portion of the wick exposed to neutron activation.

solved using an in-house developed ODE solver based on SciPy Python package. It was assumed that the system operates continuously for 10 years at full power (200 kWt) with an integrated flux Φ equal to $(1.23 \pm 0.01) \times 10^{13}$ n/cm²s. This value has been tallied in the portion of the wick confined within the reactor boundary, as shown in Figure 4.

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} C_0 \\ C_1 \\ \dots \\ C_N \end{bmatrix} = \Phi \begin{bmatrix} -\sigma_0 & \sigma_{1 \rightarrow 0} & \dots & \dots \\ \sigma_{0 \rightarrow 1} & -\sigma_1 & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & -\sigma_N \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_0 \\ C_1 \\ \dots \\ C_N \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -\lambda_0 & \lambda_{1 \rightarrow 0} & \dots & \dots \\ \lambda_{0 \rightarrow 1} & -\lambda_0 & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & -\lambda_N \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} C_0 \\ C_1 \\ \dots \\ C_N \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The second step of the analysis consists in the modelling of the radioactive source and the electronic target in the particle transport code OpenMC [9]. This step is based on the assumption that all the dose comes from the interaction with γ rays. This is justified by the energy range of the β^- spectrum (see Figure 6) and by the presence of the heat pipes' wall, made of TZM alloy ($\approx 99.42\%$ Mo, $\approx 0.5\%$ Ti and $\approx 0.08\%$ Ti), that attenuates most of the electron flux. The penetration depth of 1 MeV electrons is estimated at about 0.066 cm [10], assuming a pipe density of 10.22 g/cm³, which is on the same order as the pipe thickness. The attenuation is mostly due to non-radiative processes for the typical Q-value of β^- decays (see Figure 5). The source has been modelled in OpenMC and implements these components: the final portion of one HP, which is modelled as a linear, uniform and isotropic γ source concentric to the HP; The 0.07 cm thick pipe's wall; the final part of the reactor shield, composed by a first layer (4 cm thick) of lithium hydride and a second layer (1 cm thick) of tungsten; a 0.5 cm thick cylindrical element with a radius of 0.5 cm and made of SiO₂, which is used as surrogate for a electronic component. Finally, a thin layer Stainless Steel (SS) is placed below the SiO₂ target to mimic the presence of interfering components, such as the energy conversion system, or ad hoc electronic shield. ENDF/B-VIII.0 cross section libraries [6] have been used.

3. RESULTS

The solution of the burnup equation (Equation 1) is reported in Figure 7. In particular, the concentrations of each radioactive nuclide are reported, along with their activities. The predominant contribution

Figure 5. Electron stopping power (left) and radiative yield (right) in molybdenum [10].

Figure 6. β^- spectrum and photon emission intensity for Na-24 decay [11].

to the activity is given by Na-24 decay in Mg-24 (2.66 GBq/g or 1.70 GBq/cm per single HP), with negligible contributions from the other nuclides, despite the comparable concentration of some isotopes, such as K-40, Cl-36 and Ca-41. Because of the relatively short decay time of Na-24 (≈ 15 h), secular equilibrium is achieved soon compared to the reactor operating lifetime of 10 y. Because of that, and due to the predominant effect of Na-24, the radioactive source has been modelled in OpenMC as constant in time and considering only γ rays emission coming from Mg-24 relaxation (see Figure 6). Figure 8 (left) shows the geometrical setup and the photon flux spatial distribution generated from the activity of one HP.

On the right graph of Figure 8 is reported the absorbed dose in SiO₂ as function of the distance d from the upper end of the pipe, with and without thin the SS layer. At $d = 40$ cm it is recorded a dose between 0.3 and 0.5 Mrad (depending on the thickness of the SS layer), which adds up to the space and primary reactor radiation. The Dose beyond 40 cm has been estimated using a fit function based on the superposition of infinite point sources arranged on a line of length L_{source} . Each provides contribution $D_0 / (d + z)^2 dz$ with z the distance from the pipe upper end and the point source position and D_0 a fit parameter. The overall effect is given by the integration over the source length, as shown in Equation 2.

$$f(d) = \int_0^{L_{source}} \frac{D_0}{d+z} dz = D_0 \left(\frac{1}{d} - \frac{1}{d+L_{source}} \right) \quad (2)$$

It turns out that the activation of a single HP in a 200 kWt reactor and the long operational time is sufficient for damaging the electrical components if are not placed sufficiently far away from the source,

considering that literature reports a maximum γ -dose tolerance for rad-hard electronics between 0.1 to 10 Mrad [12, 13, 14].

Figure 7. Isotope relative concentration (left) and their activity per grams of initial sodium (right).

Figure 8. Spatial distribution of photon flux (left), flux relative error (middle) and dose on SiO_2 chip (right). The results refer to the contribution of a single heat pipe.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed at investigating the issue of HP neutron activation in space reactors. The analysis was based on a test case 200 kWt reactor employing sodium-filled HPs specifically designed for space applications and characterised by an epithermal spectrum. The neutron activation study tracked the activation and decay of sodium impurities revealing that they provide a minor contribution to the fluid activation, with Na-24 being the primary radioactive source with intensity orders of magnitude higher. The activity reaches an equilibrium in ≈ 5 days with an intensity of 2.66 GBq per gram of sodium. Each decay of Mg-24 produces two γ photons of 1.368 MeV and 2.745 MeV with $\approx 99.9\%$ occurrence which leads to non negligible doses in electronic components, comparable with tolerances expressed in literature for rad-hard components (0.1-10 Mrad). This issue must be addressed through careful design

strategies. For instance, the reactor cooling system could consist of two distinct HP clusters: one dedicated to direct core cooling and the other linked to the energy conversion units. The thermal coupling between the two could be placed within the shield, far from the active region. Alternatively, sensitive electronic component should be placed farther away ($\gg 1 m$) from the HPs upper end or specific electronics' shield needs to be used to attenuate photon current. This activation analysis focused a subset of impurities that are most likely to be found in commercial-grade sodium. However, future studies should consider a wider range of elements, especially those that have high capture cross section and produce radionuclides with short half-life. Additionally, this work considered an activation region delimited by the reactor boundaries, however, additional activation could happen in the shield, especially if it is made of strong moderator such as LiH. Further studies are needed to address this issue and evaluate the impact of fluid activation in shielding design and material selection.

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